

TWO INTERPRETATIONS OF ONE IMAGE

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10.5281/zenodo.20025624

Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада ўзбек халқининг икки истеъдодли шоирлари Рауф Парфи ва Муҳаммад Алиларнинг Виктор Харага бағишланган шеърлари қиёсан таҳлилга тортилади. Таҳлил жараёнида шоирларнинг бир образга бўлган икки хил муносабати гўзал ташбеҳлар орқали ўз ифодасини топади.

Калит сўзлар: лирик кечинма, лирик қахрамон, мунособат, ташбеҳ, қиёсий таҳлил, талқин, илҳом, истеъдод, шоир шахси, шеър дуёси.

Annotation: In this article poems of two talented uzbek national poets – Rauf Parfi and Muhammad Ali, devoted to Victor Jara are comparatively analyzed. During analysis of two different poets' attitudes through image are reflected in beautiful illustrations.

Key words: lyrical experience, lyric hero, attitude, literary comparison, comparative analysis, interpretation, inspiration, talent, personality of the poet, world of poetry.

Аннотация: В этой статье сравниваются стихи двух талантливых, узбекских, народных поэтов Рауфа Парфи и Мухаммад Али посвященных творчестве Виктора Хары. Во время анализа можно увидеть разные отношения поэтов которые выражены с красивыми примерами на основе аллегории.

Ключевые слова: лирическое переживание, лирический герой, отношение, аллегория, сопоставительный анализ, вдохновение, талант, личность поэта, мир поэзии.

R.Parfi is a poet who rose modern poetry to a new level. His style of poetic observation has grown into a separate creative school in our poetry and has laid the groundwork for the emergence of a new direction in modern poetry. The poet's feelings are pure and at the same time wailful. It is the poet's attitude to man, to his will. In his poems he beautiful illustrates image of nature and spirit of Motherland by the philosophical considerations, which do not have analogues.

Almost all poems of the sensitive poet praise human's will and freedom, and there is a sense of contempt for those who violate them. For example, the poem "The Last Song of Victor Jara" is well known to all of us. In the same way, another poem about the way of life of Victor Hara can be found among the works of talented poet Muhammad Ali. It is "Letter to the beloved of Chilean Poet Victor Jara". It is known that Chilean nightingale Victor Jara was executed in horrible way – his fingers were cut, and after it - his hands, then he was killed by junta led by Augusto Pinochet in front of five thousand inmates at one of the central stadiums in Santiago for his revengeful poems, for his anthem for freedom. R.Parfi unveils fully this story in his poem. Poet Muhammad Ali composed his poem on the base of the appeal of lyric hero – Victor Jara to his beloved one. Rauf Parfi used modern poetry to form the image of the hero for freedom. He places the psychological details that carry the main meaning upon the request of figurative logic. They become turning points in the direction of experience. In his poem, Muhammad Ali uses his pen to convey Victor Jara's experiences in a dramatic way. Rauf Parfi's portrayal of the freedom fighter begins with the following lines:

Oh, it's so hard to sing the last song,
In front of Victor Jara's eyes
They ruined his native land -
His sacred guitar with seven rings.
Then cut his fingers
To the tunes of his songs.
Not one,
Not two,
Not three...
Murderers cut his fingers –
His ten children indeed.

Do really God created them!

The poem's expression is close to the epic and impresses as old saga. However, the laconic description of the state of affirmation, denial, repetition, tragedy, subjugates it to the lyrical regularities.

Heavy thoughts throughout the poem, coupled with repetitions such as "It's hard to sing the last song", "Heavy, very heavy", "Heavy," inform readers about Victor Jara's state of mind, his courage, his devotion to his beliefs and lead to an end:

Oh, the last song...
To sing...
I must

There are many ingenious poems written by R.Parfi. In general, Rauf Parfi's poems sing of the complex nature of man, his unstable nature. A closer look reveals the discovery of the human's "I" in this poem.

Muhammad Ali uses simple lyric rules unlike Rauf Parfi, but keeping melodiousness over the whole poem, expressed lyrical feelings in the name of Victor Jara. Victor Jara, before the tragedy, tells her beloved that she must stand tall and be proud:

"O Chile belle! Stand tall,
Don't cry in vain.
Wait for fruits of sacrifice,
Withstand a misery
Withstand.
It is always a blessing to die for freedom!
People are amazed by the courage of mine.
One, who is real man,
Seeks for shining decease,
Seeks for.

Throughout the poem, the lyric hero's dedication, heroism, and patriotism are praised. By dint of appeal of Victor Jara to his sweetheart, poet glorifies ideas of sacrifice for the country, for the freedom and emphasize Jara's wish to her bellowed to withstand all the sorrows:

Oh, the fate promises you pains!
No, you don't need a shelter.
The death of glorious singer of you
Became a soil to the great idea.

To the great idea!

These lines describe a bitter pity of Victor Jara to his beloved saying, "Oh, the fate promises you pains!", but the words "The death of glorious singer of you became a soil to the great idea. To the great idea!" declares that the poet sacrificed his life for the freedom of his country and that he is proud of it. Victor Jara's leading of his nation to the freedom, to the feat is well illustrated by Muhammad Ali. The scope of poetic abilities of the poet and his state of feelings are reunited and expressed in his poems lyrically.

The courage of the hero who fights for freedom captivates the reader with two different portrayals given by two artists - Rauf Parfi and Muhammad Ali. The two lyrical experiences of two artists inspire the reader to love and protect the Motherland and know the value of freedom.

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